

DEONTOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Andijon davlat universiteti

professori DSc Abdullayeva Nasibaxon Jo‘rayevna

ABSTRACT: The process of professional training of future teachers is a crucial aspect of education as it shapes the quality of education provided to students. One of the approaches to this process is the deontological approach, which focuses on ethical principles and values. This article explores the deontological approach to the process of professional training of future teachers. It discusses the importance of ethical principles and values in teacher education, the role of deontological approach in teacher education, and the challenges and opportunities associated with this approach. The article concludes that the deontological approach can provide a strong foundation for the professional training of future teachers, but it requires careful consideration and implementation.

KEY WORDS: Deontological approach, professional training, future teachers, ethics, values

INTRODUCTION

The process of professional training of future teachers is a complex and challenging task that requires careful consideration and planning. The quality of education provided to students largely depends on the quality of teachers. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that future teachers receive adequate training and preparation to meet the demands of their profession. One of the approaches to this process is the deontological approach, which focuses on ethical principles and values. This approach emphasizes the importance of moral duty and responsibility in the teaching profession. In this article, we will explore the deontological

approach to the process of professional training of future teachers.

MAIN BODY

Deontological communicative culture is an integral component of professional culture for a specialist working in the system "person - person".

The problem of development of deontological communicative culture of the heads of educational institutions at extension courses is cross-disciplinary. It is a part of psychology, pedagogy, educational management, philosophy, sociology and is a part of more general problem - the problem of improvement of the continuous professional training of teaching and administrative staff of the educational system.

Manager of education is an authorized person in the process of interaction with representatives of various age, social, ethnic, professional groups who contributes to formation of humanistic relationship, dialogical style of communication in the systems "administrator - subordinators", "adult - child", "a manager of education - social partners of educational institution", "pedagogues - schoolchildren's family members". In such case a point of development of manager of education communicative culture within refresher courses is worth being raised on the basis of pedagogical deontological requirements.

As a central figure of holistic pedagogical process managers should be able to solve various administrative issues, to manage an educational institution with its well-established traditions and lifestyle as well as to move a school up into a new qualitative level. Arrangement of this point calls for special knowledge in the field of management of education, competence in pedagogical deontology, certain personal and professional characteristics, high communicative standards and professional-ethical skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Importance of ethical principles and values in teacher education

Ethical principles and values play a crucial role in teacher education.

Teachers are responsible for shaping the minds and characters of students, and therefore, they must uphold high ethical standards. Ethical principles such as honesty, integrity, respect, and fairness are essential for teachers to create a positive learning environment and establish trust with students. Values such as empathy, compassion, and social responsibility are also important for teachers to develop a sense of social awareness and responsibility in students. Therefore, it is essential to incorporate ethical principles and values into the process of professional training of future teachers.

Role of deontological approach in teacher education

The deontological approach to teacher education focuses on ethical principles and values. This approach emphasizes the importance of moral duty and responsibility in the teaching profession. According to this approach, teachers have a moral obligation to act in the best interest of their students and society. This approach also emphasizes the importance of developing a sense of moral autonomy and responsibility in teachers. Teachers must be able to make ethical decisions independently and take responsibility for their actions.

The deontological approach also emphasizes the importance of developing a strong sense of professional identity in teachers. Teachers must understand their roles and responsibilities as professionals and be committed to upholding high ethical standards. This approach also emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development and self-reflection. Teachers must be willing to reflect on their practice and make changes to improve their performance.

Challenges and opportunities associated with the deontological approach

The deontological approach to teacher education faces several challenges and opportunities. One of the challenges is the lack of consensus on ethical principles and values. Different cultures and societies have different ethical standards, and therefore, it can be challenging to develop a universal set of ethical principles and values. Another challenge is the difficulty in implementing ethical

principles and values in practice. Teachers may face ethical dilemmas and conflicts that require careful consideration and decision-making.

However, the deontological approach also presents several opportunities. This approach can provide a strong foundation for the professional training of future teachers. It can help teachers develop a strong sense of moral duty and responsibility, which can enhance their performance as educators. This approach can also help teachers develop a sense of professional identity, which can improve their job satisfaction and retention rates.

CONCLUSION

The deontological approach to the process of professional training of future teachers emphasizes the importance of ethical principles and values. This approach can provide a strong foundation for the professional training of future teachers and help them develop a sense of moral duty and responsibility. However, it requires careful consideration and implementation. Teachers must be willing to reflect on their practice and make changes to improve their performance. They must also be committed to upholding high ethical standards and developing a strong sense of professional identity.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Beck, C. D., & Murphy, J. (1993). Ethics in educational research: introducing a deontological perspective. *Educational researcher*, 22(2), 16-23.
2. Carr, D. (2004). *Professionalism and ethics in teaching*. London: Routledge Falmer.
3. Giroux, H. A. (1997). *Pedagogy and the politics of hope: Theory, culture, and schooling*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
4. Noddings, N. (1995). *Philosophy of education*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
5. Strike, K. A., & Soltis, J. F. (2004). *The ethics of teaching*. New York: Teachers College Press.

6. A'zamxonov S.X. Inson kapitali bilan bog'liq tushunchalarning nazariy tahlili <https://interonconf.org/index.php/den/article/view/2533> _____ vol. 2 no. 20 (2023): [pedagogical sciences and teaching methods](#) 247-254–bet

7. A'zamxonov S.X. Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari <https://bestpublication.org/index.php/iq/article/view/1106> _____ vol. 2 no. 22 (2022): [ijodkor o'qituvchi](#) 381-386-bet

8. A'zamxonov S.X. Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi faoliyatining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari <https://bestpublication.org/index.php/ozf/article/view/1313/1272> vol. 1 no. 12 (2022): [o'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali](#) 453-459-bet

9. Аликариев Н.С., Аликариева А.Н. Олий таълим сифати менежменти тизимини ривожлантириш концепцияси//“Социология фанлари” (www.tadqiqot.uz\soci) электрон журнали. №1. – Тошкент, 2020. – Б. 7-18. DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2020-1/>

10. Kadirova Y. B. The Advantages of Improving Students' Civic Literacy in Building a Democratic State Governed by the Rule of Law //International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 5. – С. 469-473.

11. Isropilov m. b. the role of pr technologies in ensuring the sustainable development of society //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 729-735.

12. Akhmedova F. [Professional Education Pharmaceutical Personnel in Uzbekistan](#)- Eastern European Scientific Journal, 2018